

INCREASING THE SOCIAL ACTIVITY OF FEMALE STUDENTS IS A REQUIREMENT OF THE TIMES.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17623171>

Abstract. *This article analyzes the relevance of increasing the social activity of female students, their place and role in society. It also highlights the role of educational institutions, public organizations and the family in developing the spiritual, intellectual and professional potential of female students. The article discusses social, cultural and digital factors that contribute to increasing the activity of female students in modern conditions.*

Keywords: *Female students, social activism, education, spirituality, digital literacy, women's leadership, youth policy, volunteerism, community development.*

Introduction. In today's era of globalization and digital society, the development of the country directly depends on the social activity of young people, especially female students. The future of each society is determined by the worldview, activity and initiative of the younger generation. Therefore, strengthening the participation of female students in social life, fully realizing their intellectual and spiritual potential is one of the urgent issues of today.

Main part: Students are emerging not only as learners, but also as active participants in social change in society. Increasing their social engagement is important in the following areas: Spiritual and moral education. When students, with a deep understanding of their national values, traditions and culture, master modern knowledge and technologies, this will serve to strengthen a healthy environment in society. They can be a source of inspiration not only for their peers, but also for the younger generation in society.

It is also important to promote the successful experiences of active girls through social media and use them as examples for other peers. This not only increases motivation, but also strengthens the positive image of girls in society.

Participation in social projects. Active participation of students in social projects, volunteer programs, environmental and cultural events develops their leadership qualities. Such activities contribute not only to personal growth, but also to the formation of a sense of social responsibility.

Social activism is the need of the hour. Today, the social activism of students is becoming a factor determining not only their personal development, but also the development of the entire society. Social activism is a person's participation in the life of society, initiative, responsibility and civic position.

Digital literacy and information culture. Nowadays, knowledge of digital technologies has become a necessity for every age group. Increasing digital literacy among students, creating a healthy information space on social networks, and protecting them from fake information are important forms of social activism. The role of educational institutions. Higher education institutions should equip female students not only with knowledge, but also with the skills to be

active in social life. Involving female students in structures such as the "Youth Parliament", "Women's Leadership Club", and "Student Council" is an effective tool for increasing their social activity.

Education and professional growth. The active participation of girls in higher education, their involvement in scientific research, and their participation in startups and innovative ideas also contribute to the country's economic development. Therefore, it is important to expand the system of women's leadership, mentorship programs, grants, and competitions in higher education institutions.

The role of family and society. The activity of female students largely depends on their family environment and parental support. Therefore, it is important to form a culture in society that values the social activity of girls and encourages them in every way.

Ways to increase the social activity of students. Innovative approaches in educational institutions. The use of modern pedagogical technologies in higher education institutions plays an important role in increasing the social activity of students. Mechanisms for increasing the activity of female students in educational institutions

Educational institutions play an important role in increasing the social activity of female students. It is necessary to further improve the activities of girls' councils, mentoring programs and women's clubs in universities and institutes. Through such structures, girls will have the opportunity not only to express their opinions, but also to directly participate in solving problems.

By organizing social projects, debates and specialized training during the educational process, it is possible to develop leadership, teamwork, critical thinking and communication skills in girls. Because these skills will be of great help in their professional lives later. The role of family and society in increasing activity. The social activity of female students does not depend only on the education system.

Family and society are also important factors in this process. Parents should encourage girls' activity, express confidence in their chosen direction, and support them ideologically and spiritually. By strengthening a positive attitude towards the role of women in society and eliminating stereotypes, a wider path will be opened for girls' activity. Today, in our country, opportunities are expanding for the realization of girls' intellectual potential through the "Women's Notebook", "Women's Advisory Councils", as well as Presidential Schools, technoparks and startup programs aimed at increasing women's activity in socio-political life.

With confidence in the future. The young generation, especially female students, determine the face of the future society. Their social activity is not only personal success, but also an important indicator of the development of the state. Therefore, every educational institution, team and leader should value the initiative of female students and consider it their priority to show confidence in them.

Today, the expansion of women's activities in the world, their rise in the fields of politics, business, science and technology, is also a great source of inspiration for female students of Uzbekistan.

After all, active, educated, and enterprising girls are the guarantee of the bright future of the nation and the prosperity of the Motherland.

By establishing “Leadership Schools”, girls can develop independent thinking, speech culture, and management skills. Through “mentoring programs”, active female leaders will help female students gain experience and prepare them for social life. The establishment of an

“Active Female Student Club” in each university can be an effective platform for supporting their initiatives. Expand volunteering and social service activities. Volunteering is the most effective way to increase the social responsibility of young people, especially female students.

Therefore: It is necessary to widely involve female students in volunteer programs in the fields of ecology, education, healthcare, culture, and sports. It is advisable to introduce a system of encouraging girls who are active in volunteering at the state or university level.

Formation of information and communication culture. In the digital society, it is important to disseminate healthy information through social networks and protect young people from various foreign ideas. In this regard: It is necessary to organize seminars and trainings on information culture and media literacy among students. Establishing projects such as the “Active Women Online Forum” or the “Student Media Center” will strengthen their social activity in the virtual environment.

Social partnership and international cooperation. To increase the activity of female students, it is necessary to expand cooperation with international organizations, non-governmental organizations, and business structures. Involving girls in practical projects and innovative clusters based on social partnership will increase their professional and civic activity. The social activity of female students is the foundation for their future professional success and active citizenship in society. Therefore, every teacher, parent, and community representative should believe in the potential of girls and support them. After all, an active, educated, and enterprising female student is the leading woman of tomorrow, a selfless person for the prosperity of the homeland.

Ways to develop the leadership potential of female students. In today's era of globalization, female students need to be not only knowledgeable specialists in their field, but also individuals with leadership skills in society. To this end, the establishment of leadership schools, psychological trainings, and social project laboratories in higher education institutions will yield useful results. Through such initiatives, girls will learn to creatively approach problems, work in a team, and defend their opinions with justification

Also, participation in international exchange programs, participation in competitions and grants in their specialization, and giving lectures at scientific conferences increase the activity of students and take them to a new level. Especially in the digital era, mastering information technologies, being active in online education and startup projects strengthens their self-confidence.

Spiritual and cultural education is the basis of social activity

The social activity of female students is closely related to their spiritual world. By developing a reading culture among girls, preserving national values and traditions, and actively participating in art and sports events, patriotism, civic responsibility, and social awareness are formed in them.

In this process, teachers, psychologists, and coaches have a great responsibility. Because they are not only educators, but also people who guide young people to choose the right path in life. Therefore, every student needs moral encouragement, attention, and trust so that they feel like an active member of society.

Conclusion. Increasing the social activity of students is not just propaganda, but a strategic direction that ensures the future of the nation. The more active they are, the stronger the renewal, growth and stability in society will be. Every educational institution, public organization and family must contribute to this process. Shunday ekan, har bir talaba-qiz o‘z

imkoniyatlarini ro'yobga chiqarish, mamlakat taraqqiyotida faol ishtirok etish, o'z zamonasining yetakchi ayoliga aylanish yo'lida qat'iyat bilan harakat qilishi davr talabi hisoblanadi. Every student studying in higher education institutions today is creating the foundation of tomorrow's science, education, culture, and governance system. Therefore, trusting them, opening doors to opportunities, and supporting their initiatives is one of the most important demands of the era.

After all, an active student is the pillar of a creative society, a guarantee of the prosperity of the Motherland and the happiness of the nation.

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